

AMPAC-Net

Workshop summary

16.-18.01.2023

ESA Polar Science Cluster Community Action project

AMPAC-Net

Arctic Methane and Permafrost challenge - Network

Workshop report, 16.-18.01.2023

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Executive summary

The aim of AMPAC-Net is to facilitate AMPAC – the Arctic Methane and Permafrost Challenge which is a transatlantic initiative by NASA and ESA. The overall objective of a reinforced collaboration between the European, American, and Canadian community is to reach out and inform the various science groups about AMPAC to bring different communities, research groups and individuals together which have the potential to advance the mutual goals of AMPAC and its three working groups.

This document summarises the second community workshop which took place on 16.-18.01.2023, at FMI Helsinki. It targeted the discussion of future research priorities for all aspects of methane in the Arctic, including observations and modelling and the formulation of concrete actions to be achieved within specific timeframes. More than 40 researchers from more than 10 countries participated. A series of high-level publications is expected as the outcome of this workshop.

Ten concrete publication ideas which could be addressed within the next 12 months have been proposed which in most cases cover several topics discussed at the workshop. Collaborations between European and US participants are foreseen in all cases. The topics of all AMPAC working groups will be addressed. A mixture of general review papers, data collection and benchmarking as well as specific studies was proposed. The latter include

- the focus on the shoulder season across different in situ observation types,
- the added value of isotopes for inversions,
- heterogeneity aspects of Arctic landcover and
- trend analyses in inversions.

Further activities have been proposed which could be started during the AMPAC-Net time frame: general white paper, consideration of abrupt thaw features visible from space, preparing inversions for RECCAP-2 follow-on, thaw period length comparisons, late winter emissions quantification, and addressing the role of geological seeps. In addition, tests of schemes potentially applicable for future missions in advanced stage (Sentinels) focusing on SAR and hyperspectral observations have been suggested. Advancement can be also expected through improvement of wetland characterization through VHR data focusing on specific wetlands features/zones (small lakes and lake margins).

1 Meeting overview

1.1 Purpose of the workshop

Central for community engagement is the organization of at least two workshops. Outcomes feed into task 2 (catalogue set-up) to task 5 (Bottom-up Top-down investigations) of AMPAC-Net (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Work logic of AMPAC-Net

The workshops aim at reinforcement of scientific collaborations between the European community and the American and Canadian community and the advancement of the AMPAC Scientific Agenda.

1.2 Workshop schedule

Monday: Status update of AMPAC activities

13:00-13:15 Welcome and Overview AMPAC (Dirk Schüttemeyer, ESA)

13:15-14:15:

- ESA AMPAC-Net (Annett Bartsch, b.geos)
- ESA MethaneCAMP (Johanna Tamminen, FMI)
- NASA ABoVE (Charles Miller, NASA)

- FMI activities (Jouni Pulliainen, FMI)

14:15-15:00 Round the table participant introduction/interests

15:00-15:30 Coffee & Posters

15:30-17:30 Working group introductions (observations, model linkage, future missions) and keynotes for WG topics

- Observations (Hartmut Bösch, UB; Mathias Goeckede, MPI; Annett Bartsch, b.geos)
- Model linkage (Jennifer Watts, Woodwell; Sander Houweling, VU)
- Future missions (including COMET) (Andreas Fix, DLR)

Tuesday - working group discussions and benchmarking

9:00-9:30 Summary from keynotes Monday and breakout preparation.

9:30-10:30 1st breakout round WG gap analyses.

10:30-11:00 Coffee & Posters

11:00-12:00 2nd breakout round WG gap analyses (people changing groups)

12:00-13:30 Lunch break

13:30-14:00:

- Wetland upscaling requirements keynote (Mckenzie Kuhn, UNH on BAWLD)
- Benchmarking wetlands, what datasets are available (review of catalog – Annett Bartsch, b.geos and AWI).

14:00-14:30:

- Methane concentration keynote (Hannakaisa Lindqvist, FMI),
- Benchmarking methane concentration, what datasets are available (review of catalog – Johanna Tamminen, FMI and AWI).

14:30-15:00 Coffee & Posters

15:00-17:00 Breakouts benchmarking (2 rounds, 1h)

17:00-17:30 Reporting from breakouts

Wednesday – Bottom-up Top-down and paper planning

9:00-9:30 BUTD keynote RECCAP2 Permafrost (Gustaf Hugelius, SU)

9:30-10:30 BUTD breakout 1

10:30-11:00 Coffee & Posters

11:00-12:00 BUTD breakout 2

12:00-13:30 Lunch break

13:30-14:00 Reporting from BUTD breakouts

14:00-15:00 Discussion of required activities, publication plans

15:00-15:30 Coffee & Posters

15:30-17:00 Discussion of required activities, publication plans

17:00-17:30 Wrap

2 Meeting summary

2.1 Overview

40 of the 48 registered participants could eventually take part in person. Further approximately 10 persons from FMI and other Helsinki institutions joined for parts of the meeting.

AMPAC and related projects (ESA and NASA) have been presented on the first day followed by an introduction round by the participants. The last session on Monday included the keynotes for the three working group topics. A summary from the first day was presented on Tuesday morning, as a starting point of the breakout discussions. Four breakouts run in parallel, three with dedicated working group topics and one on without topic. This was continued after the coffee break with new group members. The afternoon started with keynotes on benchmarking with breakouts right after. The day was concluded with reports from all breakouts on this day. The topic bottom-up top-down was started with a keynote on Wednesday morning. Breakouts and reporting followed. The afternoon was dedicated to the revision of all identified issues and topics, prioritisation and action assignments.

Figure 2: Participants of the AMPAC-Net workshop at FMI, 18.01.2023

2.2 Keynote summaries

Working group I keynotes highlighted the lack of in situ observations in general and those suitable for atmosphere retrievals in particular. Also differences in data availability from satellites are of concern. This specifically applies to the winter season. TROPOMI provides more measurements for this period than GOSAT, but data availability nevertheless remains insufficient for this time period.

The loss of in situ observations for Russia has been discussed. This will reduce the regions with good data coverage from 55% to 36%. Remote sensing products might be able to help with the identification of regions in other countries which are representative for the Russian sites and other regions not covered. Disturbances (abrupt thaw features) and landscape heterogeneity need to be considered in this context.

There is a lack of reliable soil moisture estimates and time series over high latitudes due to retrieval issues which to a large extent relate to spatial resolution. Land surface features which represent wetness gradients can be used as proxy but lack dynamics. Feasible on coarse resolution is inundation monitoring, however partitioning into different wetland features as would be required is not feasible with such approaches. SAR based regular acquisitions as might become available through future missions could potentially provide the required detail.

Similar issues with scales have been highlighted in the context of working group II presentations. A reliable representation of landscape wetness and aquatic systems is needed for upscaling. Wetlands need to be separated from lakes. In addition, the heterogeneity of water bodies with respect to CH₄ fluxes are key. Carbon source availability variations over time (unfrozen soil conditions) need to be considered (including winter). The importance of isotopes has been stressed as important with respect to inversions.

Future mission developments (working group III) are important for specifically atmosphere, hyperspectral and SAR missions. Advance is expected by synergistic use of the different instruments. But dedicated validation strategies are needed for the Arctic. In this context it should be also considered what additional information is required from in situ and models to eventually address the AMPAC questions.

Top down estimates show that natural emissions from wetlands are dominating emissions at high northern latitudes. The differences between bottom-up and top-down are however large. This relates specifically to differences in attribution of sources.

2.3 Breakout outcomes

Breakout sessions covered all working group topics and several sessions had been started without a predefined topic. **Key issues which were discussed in most themes were the non-growing season gap, the need for super sites/reference sites, landscape heterogeneity and seasonality.**

Key points were:

- WG I incl. wetland benchmarking
 - A special focus on lake margins is needed
 - Supersites need to be defined
 - non growing season observations are needed, considering also plant species and transport in winter
 - Maximized use of existing datasets for concentrations, comparison of concentrations

- Vegetation in wetlands needs to be assessed together with hydrological regimes. There are large spatial uncertainties
- spatial heterogeneity, incl. small lakes and emergent vegetation, consideration of landform types
- inter-annual shifts in wetting/drying need to be considered in addition to seasonality

- WG II incl. BUTD
 - Modified priors are needed, from e.g. data-driven bottom-up scaling
 - Tweaking global products for the permafrost region to get better representation
 - More model runs are needed
 - CMIP6 models do not yet include permafrost wetlands
 - Potentially focus on key region (tbd) processing
 - Consideration of seasonality is needed

- WG III
 - Non-growing season gap needs to be addressed
 - Reference sites are needed
 - landcover heterogeneity needs to be addressed
 - low signals, e.g. GHGSat should be tested
 - diverse observing system from different satellites is needed
 - mission continuity needs to be ensured
 - operational lidar needed

- open discussion
 - non-growing season dynamics and shoulder season need to be addressed
 - landscape heterogeneity and seasonality are key
 - need for supersites, forest sites to be included as well

In total 40 topics have been identified as of interest. This list was eventually reviewed regarding priority and feasibility within a certain time frame. 10 concrete publication ideas which could be addressed within the next 12 months (priority 1) have been proposed which in most cases cover several of the topics each.

The planned priority 1 publications specifically target the maximized use of existing datasets, for both land and atmosphere issues. Current wetland characterization schemes are addressed from various sides, discussing issues of used schemes as well as landscape heterogeneity. There are larger spatial uncertainties than flux uncertainty. Key sites need to be defined for benchmarking for which spatial variability needs to be quantified and evaluated regarding their representativeness. There has been general agreement that bottom-up estimates are too large. Related issues include oxidation and uncertainties in landcover maps. Shoulder season monitoring has been also identified as one of the key gaps. As there is a lack of observations from satellites, the use of commercial aeroplanes should be considered. A dedicated publication on summarising the gaps identified needs to be prepared. Recommendations for future missions have been suggested, e.g. that the continuity of operational LEO SWIR and IR sensors needs to be ensured, satellite systems need to be complemented with dense ground based networks, timing of overflights to be better matched with potential emissions, and tests with high resolution sensors such as GHGSat over permafrost environments should be made. These recommendations will be summarised in a separate publication.

Future potential activities **with focus on remote sensing retrievals** including potential products from future missions at advanced stage:

- Land:
 - Remote sensing maps need to thematically differentiate wetland types by vegetation community AND hydrological regime. Interannual dynamics in wetting/drying need to be better understood and monitored. In particular the potential of monthly/biweekly SAR backscatter maps for identifying areas which undergo wet-dry transition should be investigated. This should include demonstration of use for inversions. Of specific interest in this context is L-band SAR. The utility of relevant future missions e.g. NISAR, ROSE-L, future Sentinel-1 should be investigated. Wetland information also needs to be made available for forested sites. In addition, the issue of raised peatlands needs to be addressed which have dry surfaces most of the year.
 - Lake margins are hotspots of methane emissions and need to be better characterised. The combination of different sensors may provide advance. Specifically the combination of large scale ground fast ice identification (shallow water bodies) with vegetation maps. The latter requires identification of aquatic vegetation communities. A potential mission of interest in this context is ENMAP. Tasking and testing its applicability for relevant PFTs over key sites is suggested.
 - VHR data can facilitate identification of small lakes within wetland complexes. Small lakes are more active and very important for fluxes. Their mapping would increase the precision in CH₄ budgets. The retrieval of relevant lake properties is required in addition to lake extent.
 - There is a lack of information on lake bathymetry and its change. Sensors such as Icesat should be tested.
 - Pockmark identification in lakes with suitable optical data may advance our understanding of methane release from geological seeps.

- Atmosphere:
 - The need for improvements in cloud masking has been discussed in multiple breakouts, including the issue of retrieval over clouds. Less conservative masking in validation/general use of data has been suggested. It should be investigated what information can be gained through such a strategy.

Further potential activities **with focus on remote sensing products use:**

- A regional analyses needs to be added to RECCAP2 Permafrost in hotspot regions of data overlapping with regions where we might see permafrost change
- In general, disturbance regimes need to be investigated. Fire feedbacks need to be addressed. How appropriate are models in peatlands and wetland rich regions? Measurements are needed for fire recovery trajectory and interactions with permafrost.
- Priors for inversions need to be checked specifically their uncertainties quantified. An ensemble of inversions using modified priors should be created.
- Categories used in inverse modelling should be revised using landcover/wetland maps